

ISic4426

Inscribed boundary stone

Language

Latin

Type

terminus

Material

volcanic

Object

cippus

Editor

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Autopsy

none

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Paternò

Provenance

The only record is in the manuscript collection of Gaetano Marini, whence later editions. Marini records it as being found in the 'ager Catinensis', in the locale known as 'le Timpe', and in his time preserved in front of the church of the village of Sferri

Coordinates

37.501100, 14.796780

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, lost

Physical Description

Not directly described by Marini, but the use of 'item' after an initial description of a quadrangular column of volcanic stone, with reference to ISic4425, suggests the same form

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

The text is recorded split over two lines

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

No information is preserved

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. ECL

2. KATS

Apparatus

Text from Marini

Mai, Pace, Ferrua: KAT

Translation**Commentary**

In contrast to other examples (ISic1338 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1338>] , ISic1404 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1404>] , ISic4424 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4424>]) the text of this inscription appears to be written clearly in Latin letters. Nonetheless the presence of variations on the formulation of $\overline{\text{EK}}\text{L KAT}$ which is found also in those texts, and the broadly similar geographical area of origin, strongly suggest that this stone (and also ISic4425 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4425>] and ISic4427 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4427>] reported together with this one by Marini) has a similar context, namely as a boundary stone relating to the lands of the early church in Sicily. Like Pace before him, Ferrua interpreted these in this way, and expands ECL as *ecclesiae* and KAT as *Katinensis*. This text, together with ISic4425 and ISic4427, is only reported by Gaetano Marini, and the texts in Angelo Mai, Pace, and Ferrua all derive directly from this one record. Pace understood Marini to refer to four sides of a single stone, but Ferrua more reasonably interprets the annotations of Marini to refer firstly to two sides of one stone (ISic4425: 'hinc', 'inde'); and then to two further separate texts (ISic4427: 'item altera inscripta') and in this case what appears to be 'item altera reperta in agro'. It is not impossible that this text and ISic4427 are in fact the same as the two recorded by Gualtherus (ISic1338 and ISic4424), but the differences are sufficient to suggest not.

The date of the stone is very difficult to ascertain. If the interpretation suggested by Ferrua is adopted, making this one of several boundary markers for church property from the wider area of the Catania hinterland, then a date of the fifth century AD or later seems likely. It would be possible to accept the reading of KAT as referring to Catania, without accepting the need to interpret ECL or EKL as a reference to the church.

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

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